

United States Senate

WASHINGTON, DC 20510-0803

August 10, 2020

Paul Bechly
112 Country Club Drive
Wilmington, DE 19803

Dear Paul,

I recently heard that you have received the 2020 Mensa Foundation Intellectual Benefits to Society Award. I would like to offer my warmest congratulations to you on this extraordinary achievement!

The Intellectual Benefits to Society Award is a great honor to receive as it recognizes your innovative response to climate change and its tangible benefits to society. By working alongside technical, environmental, and business representatives, you fought hard to help reduce harmful PFC emissions in our environment. This accomplishment highlights a long and fruitful career working at DuPont as a chemical engineer in Delaware and currently as a First Vice President at Morgan Stanley.

As the Ranking Member of the Environment and Public Works Committee, I am thankful for the strides you have taken to help protect our environment as this is an issue close to my heart. You should be proud of this recognition, and I know your accomplishments will serve as continued inspiration for those who follow your example and leadership. I wish you the best of luck in all that lies ahead!

With best personal regards, I am

Sincerely yours,

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Tom Carper". The signature is fluid and cursive, with the first name "Tom" and last name "Carper" clearly legible.

Thomas R. Carper
United States Senator